

RESEARCH PAPER

LENGTH - WEIGHT RELATIONSHIP AND CONDITION FACTOR OF *Clarias gariepinus* OF CROSS RIVER BASIN (NDIBE BEACH) AT AFIKPO, SOUTH EASTERN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Length- weight relationship (LWR) and condition factor (CF) of 57 *Clarias gariepinus* inhabiting Cross River basin, Ndibe beach, Afikpo was studied. The study lasted from November 2013-February 2014. The fish sampled were sexed and the lengths and weights determined using metre rule and electronic scale. The graph of length-weight relationship of males, females and both sexes were determined from the form $W = aL^b$. Other parameters including a and b correlation r, were calculated from $\text{Log}(Y) = a+b \times \text{Log}(X)$. Monthly means condition factor was calculated using $K = 100W/L^3$, the monthly total mean of length and weight of males, females and both sexes were calculated. The “b” value for the males was 1.2929, while that of the females was 1.3317 and combined sexes 1.2634. These shows negative allometric growth. Correlation coefficient (r) for males was 0.9583, for females was 0.9828 and for both sexes was 0.9474. The condition factor values ranged between 0.93-0.99. Thus, showing that the fish was in relatively good condition.

KEYWORDS: Length-weight relationship, Correlation coefficient, Condition factor, *Clarias gariepinus*

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INTRODUCTION

The African mud catfish, *Clarias* species belonging to the family clariidae has gained widespread recognition as a promising species in aquaculture production (Taiwo, 2008).

It is an economically important food fish, cultured primarily in freshwater ponds in tropical countries especially in Nigeria and in Afikpo. *Clarias gariepinus* exhibits many qualities which makes it suitable for commercial culture. These include its rapid growth, hardiness, high disease resistance, high yield potential, high fecundity, air-breathing characteristics and good market potentials (Anyanwu et al., 2007; Onyia et al., 2010). The mentioned fact necessitates a search for reliable information on the culture of *Clarias gariepinus* which is a very good species for aquaculture. *Clarias* species in some parts of Nigeria and India particularly in West Bengal is considered as a medicinal fish and traditionally remained a strike among the pregnant and lactating mothers, the elderly and children. Many a times, the consumption of this species is prescribed prophylactically to the anemic and malnourished individuals as well as for the convalescent of the patients due to the nutritional superiority. Intensive culture of *Clarias* species in several Nigerian states such as rural areas have much potential towards livelihood development; employment generation and ensuring nutritional enrichment in the regular diet among the people (Akinwale and Faturoti, 2007). *Clarias gariepinus* is a nocturnal fish like many catfish. It feeds on living as well as dead animals. It is able to crawl on dry ground to escape drying pools. Further, it is able to survive in shallow mud for long periods of time, between rainy seasons. *Clarias gariepinus* is an omnivorous fish and can survive in

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extremely harsh environmental conditions a feature that made it favourable for culture in many part of the world. *Clarias gariepinus* feeds on living as well as dead animal matters, because of its wide mouth, it is able to swallow relatively large prey whole. It has been known to take large water birds such as the common moorhen (Ekelemu and Ogba 2005; Anoop et al., 2009). Length- weight relationship (LWR) is useful tool in fish growth pattern or age determination and fishery assessment (Peple and Ofor, 2011). The condition factor often referred to as “K” provides information on the well being of a fish and is usually influenced by the fish sex, season maturity stage etc (Anyanwu et al., 2007). Thus this paper seeks to determine length - weight relationship and condition factor of *Clarias gariepinus* of Cross river basin (Ndibe beach) at Aikpo, South eastern Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Study Area

The study area is located at Cross River Basin at Afikpo, which is about 10km from Eke market (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Map of Afikpo North Local Government Area showing the sampling location in the Cross River basin (Okoh et al., 2007).

Sample Collection

A total fish of 57 was purchased from local fishers as they land at Ndibe beach. The fishers caught fish using gill net, dip net, fishing basket, pole and line fishing boats from Cross River Basin.

Laboratory Analysis

The fish was serially numbered, the total length (TL), and standard length (SL) were taken from the tip of the head to the tip of the tail respectively using a meter rule calibrated in centimeter. Their corresponding body weights were also measured with digital weighing scale to the nearest gram (Adebayo and Adesoji 2008). The fish was preserved with 100% alcohol.

Data Analysis

The mean length and weights of the classes were used for data analysis; the format accepted by FISAT . The relationship between the length (L) and weight (W) of fish was expressed by the equation (Gayanilo and Pauly, 1997).

$$W=aL^b$$

W=Weight of fish in gram

L=Total length (TL) of fish in (cm)

a=Constant intercept

b=Slope

The “a” and “b” values were obtained from a regression of the length and weight of fish the correlation (r), which is the degree of association between the length and the weight was computed from the linear regression analysis. The condition factor (k) of the experimental fish was estimated from the relationship.

$$K=\frac{100 w}{L^3}$$

where K= condition factor

W =Weight of fish

L=Length of fish.

RESULTS

The total number of sampled species of *Clarias* was 57. The total number of male sampled was 32, while the total number of females sampled was 25; the total collections were sexed and sized grouped. The male and female *C. gariepinus* were found to be ranged from 13 to 24 cm in total length and the total weights were found to range from 35 to 64g. Fig 2 and 3 show the length frequency distribution and the length - weight relationship of males and females of *C. gariepinus* in Cross- River basin (Ndibe beach). Fig 4, 5 and 6 show the regression graph for male, female and both sexes. Table 1 respectively shows the monthly mean length, weight and condition factor of male and female *C. gariepinus*. Table 2 shows the intercept, slope and correlation coefficient values of the length-weight relationship.

Table 1: The monthly mean length-weight and condition factor of male and females *C. gariepinus* in Cross-River basin (Ndibe beach).

MALES				FEMALES		
Months	L(cm)	W(g)	K	L(cm)	W(g)	K
November	18.10	55.60	0.94	18.40	54.50	0.88
December	15.50	29.00	0.79	19.08	52.00	0.75
January	17.40	47.00	0.89	16.40	48.20	0.92
February	15.80	46.00	1.17	20.30	61.00	0.73

L = Total length, W = Total Weight, K = Condition factor value

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Table 2: The regression analysis values of the graph

	Number of fish examined	Intercept (a)	Slope (b)	Regression (r)	Standard deviation
Males	32	0.1008	1.2929	0.9583	0.0704
Females	25	0.0430	1.3317	0.9828	0.0220
Both sexes	57	0.1321	1.2634	0.9474	0.0575

Fig 2: Length distribution frequency of male and female *C. gariepinus* in Cross River Basin (Ndibe Beech)

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Fig 3: Weight distribution frequency of male and female *C. gariepinus* in Cross River Basin (Ndibe Beech)

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Fig 4: Length – Weight Relationship of Male *C. gariepinus* Function: $Y = a + b$

Fig 5: Length – Weight Relationship of Female *C. gariepinus* Function: $Y = a + b * X$

Fig 6: Length – Weight Relationship of *C. gariepinus* Function: $Y = a + b * X$

DISCUSSION

Length-weight relationship and condition factor is used to study the fatness and well-being of fishes. A healthy fish which maintained dimensional equality i.e length and weight, the value of 'b' would be 3 (Uneke, 2013). 'b' values in this study for male, female and both sexes were 1.2929, 1.13317 and 1.2634 respectively and the correlation coefficient (r) values were 0.9583, 0.9828 and 0.9474 respectively indicating a negative allometric growth pattern. The 'b' value obtained in this study is supported by studies of Fafioye and Oluajo (2005) for *Clarias gariepinus*. This contrasted Anyanwu et al. (2007) study that reported 'b' value of 2.8412 for females, 1.2713 for males and 1.8776 for combined sexes in *C. gariepinus*. However the growth patterns were negative allometric. According to Uneke (2013) LWR is an important factor in the biological study of fishes which is greatly affected by many factors related to population variability and thus may be responsible for the above variables in the LWR values. From the results, the mean condition factor values show 1.028 for male, 0.898 for female and 0.963 for both sexes. This shows that the male *C. gariepinus* was in a better condition than the female; this could be as a result of better opportunity to availability of food.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

C. gariepinus in Cross River basin, Ndibe beach exhibited negative allometric growth. The fish samples were in relatively good health condition. It recommended that the indiscriminate catching of fish with small mesh sized gears by our local fishermen should be avoided, and awareness should be created among these local fishermen to avoid destruction of these fishes. These negative activities carried out in water systems can lead to low Condition factor even of Cross River basin (Ndibe beach) water system.

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